

raised beds 40 m long × 75 cm wide. Each variety was raised in two rows made by pressing wood. The wet nursery was irrigated with well water.

The Tirunelveli District had a severe drought due to failure of the southwest monsoon. The dry spell was associated with a heavy wind, blowing at times

for more than a week. The seedlings started drying from the tip downward. Initially the margin dried up; gradually 1/3 to 2/3 of the surface of the upper portion of the lamina turned yellow and dried up.

The seedlings were scored on percentage of plants with dried leaves

(see table).

Irrespective of plant stature, 16 varieties had 10% drying. Among the remaining, 40 had 25%, 34 had 40%, 15 had 50%.

Most of the local varieties had less than 25% drying. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization HYBRID RICE

Hybrid rice research in Bihar, India

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We studied the characteristics of cytoplasmic-genetic male sterile (CMS) lines V20A, Z97A, V41A, and P203A, their maintainer (B) lines, and restorer (R) lines IR50 and IR54. The maintainer lines were 2-5 cm taller than the CMS lines, which is conducive to setting more crossed seed. Effective tiller numbers were recorded in V20A (20), Z97A (18), V41A (20), and P203A (16). In maintainer lines, tiller numbers were 17 in V20B, 13 in Z97B, 14 in V41B, and 13 in P203B.

CMS lines had better and longer tillering than maintainer and restorer lines, but poorer panicle exertion and more delayed flowering. Flowering in CMS lines (10-15 d) continued longer than in B and R lines (7-10 d). In CMS lines, stigma exertion varied from 25 to 55%; in B and R lines, it ranged from 11 to 44%. There was no obvious flowering peak in CMS lines, but B and R lines had obvious peaks. Duration of floret opening to closing was longer in CMS lines than in B and R lines.

UPRB8 and UPRB31 were analyzed as alternate sources of sterile cytoplasm. One CMS line has an alternate source of cytoplasm developed from UPRB31/IR46.

In 74 crosses made using elite cultivars with 3 CMS lines (WA type),

23 restorers, 22 partial restorers, and 16 maintainers were identified (see table).

Heterosis, heterobeltiosis, and standard heterosis for 7 agronomic traits were measured in 20 hybrids. Heterobeltiosis and standard heterosis were positive for early vegetative vigor, tillers/plant, panicle length, spikelets/panicle, and test weight, but were negative for days to heading and plant height.

V20A/IR50, V20A/IR36, V20A/IR28, Z97A/IR50, Z97A/IR36, Z97A/IR28, Z97A/IR2307-247-2-2-3, and Z97A/IR13420-6-7-3-1 were tested in dry season field trials and V20A/IET5656, Z97A/IET5656, V20A/IR50, and V20A/IR54 were tested in wet season trials. All 12 hybrids showed positive and significant heterosis, heterobeltiosis, and standard heterosis for yield. Heterosis ranged from 44.5 to 81.3% over the midparent, 8.4 to 45.0% over the better parent, and 24.0 to 72.5% over the standard check. Maximum heterosis (81.3% over the midparent) was in Z97A/IR2307-247-2-2-3.

Highest heterobeltiosis was in V20A/IR50 (41.9%) and highest standard heterosis in Z97A/IET5656 (72.5%). Most of the hybrids had more than 20% heterosis over the better parent and best commercial varieties.

No apparent improvement in grain quality characters was found in restorers, partial restorers, and maintainers.

Best isolation distance for seed production of hybrid and CMS lines was 40 m. Maximum increase in

Restorers and maintainers identified in 74 crosses of elite cultivars. Bihar, India.

<i>Good restorers</i>	
BIET360	FR43B
IET3279	IET7278
IET5656	PR103
IR46	UPR238-42-2-31
Archana	RAU4090-1
IR50	IR17494-32-1-1-3-2
IR54	Sein Ta-Lay
IET7256	BIET569
IR36	BIET944
Kiran	Br 8
MRC603-303	Pankaj
<i>Partial restorers</i>	
Panidhan 1	IET6063
UPR82	IET2881
Jaya	IET6985
TI36	IR1967-263-3-2-2-1
IET6148	IET6988
IET3273	IET3116
IET7280	IET4141
ET5995	Janki
BIET45 C	IET5741
Rasi	Br 46
CR44-35	Multani
<i>Maintainers</i>	
MW10	IET3626
Bhavani	Ratna
IR34	UPR73-23
IET6711	Mahsuri
BG90-2	P203B
IET3257	BR52-87-1
Cauvery	BIET724
IET7616	
IET4099	

percentage seed set was with 30 ppm gibberellic acid. Clipping leaves above the panicles of CMS lines increased seed set. The best planting combination was 1 row of restorer line at 10- × 10-cm spacing and 6 rows of CMS (A) line at 20- × 15-cm spacing. The best combination for CMS seed production was 4 rows of A line at 10- × 10-cm spacing and 2 rows of B line at 15- × 10-cm spacing. □